

Description of Additional Supplementary Files

File name: Supplementary Data 1

Description: List of IAA-related genes, and lists of genes forming the clusters shown in Figure 7D with indication of the presence of the auxin response cis element in their corresponding.

File name: Supplementary Data 2

Description: List of flowering time-related genes.

File name: Supplementary Data 3

Description: The source data behind the graphs in the paper.